

PEDAGOGICAL ABILITY IN SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF A FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract: In this article, you can get acquainted with the main types of pedagogical abilities, ways to develop pedagogical abilities and qualities inherent in the teacher.

Keywords: ability, pedagogical ability, empathy, perceptual ability, didactic ability, organizational skills;

The priorities of pedagogical ability are as follows:

- pedagogical tactile (pedagog's communication with students on various forms of activity is based on existing ethical principles, adherence to rules of conduct, and the right approach to them);
- pedagogical observation (the ability of the teacher to notice even the simplest features specific to the students);
- love for children (to be able to love them, to be kind to them, to share their inner experiences, feelings, dreams, life aspirations, to care in situations that are difficult for them to do);
- the need to transfer knowledge.

The main types of pedagogical ability. F.N. Gonobolin considers it important to show the following skills in the personality of the teacher: the ability to understand the reader; the ability to provide materials that all students can master, both young and psychologically; the ability to develop students' interests; organizational skills; pedagogical tact; to be able to see the results of their work and b.

Types of pedagogical skills are, first of all, counted as: pedagogical observation; pedagogical imagination (fantasy); the demand for the upbringing of character qualities; pedagogical tactile; organizational skills; ownership of speech culture; communication (inputivity); emotional sensitivity (occupational sparrowness, empathy for others, internal perception); mobility, have the ability to have a willful impact and reassure participants in the learning process; emotional stability (self-control, control and supervision); predict the future optimally; professional independence, ownership of creative ability.

V.A. Krutetsky summarizes the pedagogical skills and shows that their types are as follows.

Unique skills are also evident in talented teachers. That is: being able to perform multiple activities at the same time (for example, hearing, seeing, reading, writing, thinking, communicating, and so on.); to take a single view of two or more realities around (to be able to track the activities of other students in the classroom while hearing a student's report); extreme curiosity (every event that takes place in nature and society (Although they are the most insignificant, the most notable, the desire to know the essence of), the desire to find answers to many questions); biochemical and electrical activity of brain activity (mia is almost non-stop and takes an extremely short time “ rest ”, if uncertainties are observed during the cognition process, they are quickly eliminated; drowsiness is not a characteristic feature of gifted educators); richness of speech and fantasy (Most talented teachers have extremely rich speech in which the fantasy (imagination) ability is incredibly strong); strong memory (The ability to memorize large volumes of text, including epics, with a single reading, and to narrate it literally) is a special feature.

Didactic skills – Ability to clearly, clearly, easily explain teaching materials, arouse interest in subjects in students, shape independent thinking skills.

Academic Skills – Ability to master the basics of mathematics, physics, biology, chemistry, native language, literature, history, and other sciences.

Perceptual abilities – Ability to access the inner world of a person, psychological observation, understanding of the subtle aspects of a student’s temporary mental states.

Speech ability – The ability of an individual to express his or her feelings clearly and vividly using speech, as well as mimics, pantomime

Organizational ability – Ability to organize a team of students, to can co-organize a team, to properly organize pedagogical activities.

Authoritarian ability – Ability to gain prestige ‘among students through emotional-willed exposure.

Pedagogical imagination – the ability of the educator to anticipate the results of his actions in the educational design of the student's personality.

Attention distribution ability – Ability to describe the ability of a educator to focus on multiple processes at the same time.

Communication ability – is the ability to communicate with students, to find an effective way to approach them properly, to represent the existence of a pedagogical tactile that connects to each other in a purposeful manner.

Ways, forms, and methods of developing pedagogical ability. Like any ability, the development of pedagogical ability is required to go.

Pedagogical ability development – As an expert, only the educator (teacher) is considered to create the necessary conditions to further enrich and improve the skills specific to them.

Naturally, pedagogical ability develops in certain ways. Ways to develop pedagogical ability include

Ways to develop pedagogical ability

- Work on yourself
- Creative approach to activity
- Learning best practices
- Work based on the tradition “Teacher-student”
- Active participation in trainings
- Participation in scientific and practical conferences
- Participate in regular seminars
- Perform practical exercises independently
- Familiarize yourself with special publications
- Perform exercises based on visual materials

Certain forms are considered extremely effective in the development of pedagogical ability.

Forms of development of pedagogical ability

Anatomo-physiological preparation

Practical preparation using exercises

Achieving a certain level of ability

Learn regularly

Restore existing skills

Organization of trainings

Certain methods are also used in the development of pedagogical skills:

Methods of developing pedagogical ability

Self-awareness Self-assessment

Special Exercises Business Games

Training Getting started

Ethical qualities reflected in the personality of the teacher. Morality (lot. “moralis” – Behavior) – is one of the forms of social consciousness, regulating social relations and personal behavior, recognized by a particular society, the order to be followed, etiquette, interaction, communication, rules of conduct, set of criteria.

Ethical adjectives – adjectives that represent the non-subjectivity of the rules of interaction, communication, behavior - behavior, criteria recognized by society

in the process of organizing social relations. Ethical qualities include: morality, decency, politeness, kindness, correctness, discipline, responsibility, being with the team, faith, faith, knowledge, humility, diligence, input, fairness, conscientiousness and others.

Teacher's moral qualities – are the qualities of a teacher's social-pedagogical relationship in the process of establishing a social-pedagogical relationship, which means that the relationship is followed without deviation from the rules of communication, conduct, criteria, they are also a prayer in the form of common moral qualities. In other words, the teacher tells the students his or her morals, politeness, kindness, correctness, discipline, responsibility, ability to be with the team, faith, knowledge, humility, diligence, input, fairness, fairness, fairness, should be able to set an example with the qualities of conscientiousness and so on.

The willful and emotional qualities inherent in a teacher. The will – is the person's conscious advancement towards a specific goal, working hard.

The willful qualities – are the qualities that ensure that a person consciously moves forward towards a specific goal, and that they are among the following: strength, agility, courage, courage, perseverance, perseverance, not to deviate from the goal, not to back down, to move forward with endurance, not to shy away from difficulties, not to lose “ to lose oneself in the most difficult situations ” to be able to catch oneself “, not to despair, to be able to encourage those around you to move forward, being able to encourage them and so on.

Teacher-specific will qualities – are qualities that ensure that the student consciously moves forward, and moves toward a clear pedagogical goal, which includes: courage, bravery, perseverance in pedagogical processes. , perseverance, not to deviate from the pedagogical goal, to be able to quickly eliminate them even when physical and mental fatigue occurs in the performance of pedagogical obligations, to perform pedagogical tasks with endurance, not to shy away from difficulties, not to lose “ self-esteem ”, not to be overwhelmed by the conflicts that arise in the processes in the most difficult situations, to be able to evaluate them wisely, not to get discouraged, to be able to encourage students to move forward, to be able to encourage them, and so on.

Teacher-specific emotional qualities. Emotion (lotin emovere – excitement, restlessness, anxiety) – specific area of mood and process; grief, contentment, joy, sorrow, oysters, despair, nausea, sadness, hatred, anduh, internal experiences such as sadness, depression, vomiting, guilt, shame, confusion, disgust, surprise, curiosity, hesitation, humorous hoax. Emotional qualities –

grief, contentment, joy, sorrow, rest, despair, nausea, sadness, hatred, anduh, sadness, depression, vomiting, guilt, shame, confusion, disgust, surprise, curiosity, hesitation, adjectives that represent a sense of humor.

Teacher's emotional qualities – to the teacher the student's grief, joy, sorrow, rest, despair, hatred, anduhi, sadness, depression, confusion, disgust, surprise, curiosity, hesitation, co. 'Understanding the pants, qualities that help you feel guilty and feel ashamed, to feel the sense of humor. The emotional qualities of the teacher are reflected in the process of education, upbringing, interaction with the student in the educational institution, street and family environment. It is also important for students to master the basics of the academic subjects, to follow the rules of discipline established in the educational institution, as well as to have the necessary moral qualities in the formation of emotional qualities. After all, the teacher's emotional qualities help the student to interact, to achieve harmony, to move towards a single goal.

References:

1. N.Aliyev. B.Abdullayeva. IMPROVING SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS. WEB OF SCIENTIST: INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH JOURNAL (WoS) Volume 3, Issue 8, Aug., 2022
2. N.Aliyev. B.Abdullayeva. THEORETICAL ISSUES OF INCREASING TEACHING EFFICIENCY BASED ON MODERN ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PRIMARY CLASS. GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) Vol. 10, Issue 11, Nov. (2022) SJIF Impact Factor (2022): 7.718.
3. Abdullayeva B. S., Aliyev N. A., qizi Ergasheva D. S. Improving self-development competency of future primary class teachers //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 7. – C. 274-277.
4. Ergasheva D. FORMATION OF CORRECT READING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 1675-1678.
5. Aliyev N., Ergasheva D. METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B8. – C. 1679-1681.
6. N.Aliyev. B.Abdullayeva. IMPROVING THE COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHER IN SELF-DEVELOPMENT. Europan Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA) Vol. 3 No. 12, December 2022. Impact Factor 7.223

